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Machine Learning on Healthcare Big Data

Using Apache Spark

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Abstract. Big data and machine learning become a major procedure in scientific and healthcare applications. Apache spark is famous with its built-in machine learning capabilities and in memory cluster computing for large scale distributed computing environments. Big data needs to switch from traditional ways of applying machine learning to large amounts of data. With large datasets in healthcare and advances in machine learning machines are now well suited to treat a wide number of health issues. This work seeks to develop a model of machine learning using sparks MLlib for predicting health status. The system aims to enforce machine learning models on stroke data with certain attributes for prediction of disease. Logistic Regression, decision tree and Random forests are applied on the given dataset and comparative analysis is done using confusion matrix to compute the accuracy.

Keywords: Big data, Spark, MLlib, Stroke data, Logistic Regression, Decision tree, Random forest algorithms

1 Introduction

The heart is a fist sized Muscular organ and its function is to pump blood throughout the body[1]. It is the principal element of human body. According to World health organization (WHO) heart disease and stroke are worlds massive killers [2]. The big data available and data mining techniques through traditional systems is difficult to handle therefore demands a shift from traditional methods to handle the voluminous data. In particular to this early detection of heart disease with machine learning can therefore help patients to react to likely disease [3] in advance.

Apache Spark [3] is a data processing system developed to provide analytics that are quicker and easier to use than Hadoop Map reduce. Resilient distributed dataset [3] which is spark's soul designed to support in memory clustering and storage. Spark is designed to handle a wide area of workloads including batch processes, collaborative queries iterative algorithms and streaming. The latest spark software consists of spark core and libraries for machine learning Graph data processing (Graphx), MLlib, spark Sql and spark streaming for real time streams of data as shown in fig 1.

Fig 1 Apache Spark core and its Libraries

2 Related Work

Big data analytics nowadays has is a major issue for a large number of researchers, especially in healthcare analytics. Big Data research involving machine learning is quite involved ,many researchers have been using machine learning in healthcare recently[4].

In [5] Apache Spark is used to create a system for stroke prediction It uses distributed machine learning to train and inspect models. In [3] The Apache Spark Open Source Big Data Processing Engine built up a scalable real-time health status prediction system, tested and deployed in the cloud, where machine learning model is applied to stream data. In [1] The Scalable System is built using the Spark and Cassandra to predict heart disease. This framework focuses on the implementation of the cardiac characteristics in the real-time classification model for the monitoring of the patient's health. In [6] Studies conducted an experiment on the application of different data mining algorithms to predict heart attack and to compare the best predictive process. The research results, when using various classification algorithms in data mining, do not pose a dramatic difference in the prediction. [7]In this, researchers use structured and unstructured hospital data and Propose a new multimodal disease risk prediction algorithm (CNN-MDRP) based on the convolutional neural network.

In [8] The dissertation discusses the achievement of supporting vector machine (SVM) and logistic regression (LR) algorithms in the estimation of survival rates for patients with lung cancer, and compares. In [9] The work mainly contributes to the Creation of a real-time prediction framework for health status using big data tools, data mining and streaming information.

In [10]The work summarizes some of the current research on prediction of heart disease using data mining, analyzes algorithms of data mining and concludes which technique(s) are efficient and effective multiple data mining algorithms are applied for predicting heart attacks by evaluating the best predictive process while applying various classification algorithms it does not pose much difference in prediction.

3 Description of Proposed Work

The purpose of this study is to analyze the health care stroke data set and to develop machine learning models using various classifiers to predict the stroke. Fig 2 shows the flow of proposed work.

3.1 Dataset

In this work “Healthcare dataset stroke data” is used which is available from UCI Repository train_2v.csv is investigated and used the data contains 43400 records and 11 attributes for each record. The description of dataset is in table below

Table -1: Attribute names and description of stroke dataset

S no	Attributes	Description
1	Gender	Male or female
2	Age	Age
3	Hypertension	Hypertension
4	Heart disease	0 for absence 1 for presence of disease
5	Ever married	0 or 1
6	Work type	Children, private, never worked, govt job, self employed
7	Residence type	Rural or urban
8	Average glucose level	Average glucose level
9	Bmi	Body mass index
10	Smoking status	Never smoked formerly smoked
11	Stroke	0 or 1

In this dataset 783 have presence of stroke while 42617 have absence of stroke. Also 2062 have the disease of heart and 41338 have absence of disease it is computed using Scala language in spark environment. This paper focuses on applying different machine learning algorithms using spark MLlib to predict stroke. The data is split into training and testing dataset in 70:30 ratio. The dataset contains too much amount of categorical data which is handled using indexer and encoders.

3.2 Methodology

In the proposed study, predictive analysis of stroke is performed using MLlib of Apache Spark. Different classification algorithms are used such as logistic regression, decision trees, Random forest and then specific functions are used to measure various parameters such as accuracy using confusion matrix values.

Fig 2 Architecture of prediction system using MLlib

3.3 Machine learning algorithms

The logistic regression algorithm is used to determine the relationship between the target variables and predictive ones.

Decision tree is a classification method that is easy to interpret and popular in machine learning, and is chosen to perform the prediction. MLlib, supports decision tree algorithm and can work to create predictive scalable machine learning model, which is capable of handling huge data sets effectively[3]

Decision trees are arrays of random forests MLlib supports random forests, using both continuous and categorical features to distinguish and regress binary and multiclass. MLlib implements random forests using the most common decision tree for implementation.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (1)$$

Confusion matrix defines the performance of a classification model; it contains information regarding actual and expected classifications performed by a classifier[5]. Description of confusion matrix is given in table 2.

Table 2 Depiction of confusion matrix

	Predicted No 0	Predicted Yes 1
Actual No	TN	FP
Actual Yes	FN	TP

True positive (TP): In These we expected yes (they've got the disease) and disease is real. True negatives (TN): We expected no, and they have no illness. False positives (FP): Yes, we predicted, but they don't have the disease, currently. (And known as "Error type I.") False negative (FN): We expected no, but the disease does actually exist. (Known also as "Type II Error").

4 Results

4.1 Results of logistic Regression (LR)

Table 3 Confusion Matrix Obtained By applying LR

	Predicted-No 0	Predicted-Yes 1
Actual No	8395	10
Actual Yes	467	6

Table 3 represents the confusion matrix we got by applying logistic regression algorithm. This algorithm shows the accuracy of 94.62%.

4.2 Results using decision tree (DT)

Table 4 Confusion Matrix Obtained by Applying DT

	Predicted-No 0	Predicted-Yes 1
Actual No	8431	2
Actual Yes	491	12

Table 4 represents the confusion matrix obtained by applying decision tree it is seen the accuracy measured with the decision tree is 94.48%. The accuracy is computed applying Eq 1 on the obtained confusion matrix. All the work is carried out on spark using Scala language and Scala supports some inbuilt metrics functions like “metrics. accuracy, metrics. precision, metrics. recall” etc. to show the accuracy. The accuracy obtained from confusion matrix is same to that of accuracy obtained from the ‘metrics. accuracy’ command.

4.3 Results of Random forest classifier (RF):

Table 5 Confusion Matrix obtained by Applying RF

	Predicted-No 0	Predicted-Yes 1
Actual No	8300	2
Actual Yes	412	15

Table 5 shows the results obtained from confusion matrix by applying random forest classifier and it is computed that the accuracy of this classifier is 97%. Accuracy is computed applying Eq 1 on the confusion matrix. It can also be obtained using ‘metrics.accuracy’ function in Scala language. The reason behind obtaining such high accuracy is that the dataset is imbalanced as seen in section 3.1. The stroke dataset has been divided randomly into a training data set and a test data set, the data is split into training and testing dataset in 70:30 ratio.

In this study Several methods are used in this analysis to build our prediction framework for the health status in real time which is represented in table 6

Table 6 Experiment Environment

Software used	Node Environment
Spark 3.0	Single node
Eclipse for spark	8gb RAM
Scala 2.11.8	CPU i7 2.7ghz OS windows 64bits

5 Discussion

This work is done in windows platform on single machine with i7 processor and 8 gb RAM. Healthcare stroke dataset is imported to spark session then data is analyzed filtered and preprocessed using different techniques in the Scala language. The dataset is split into two sets and around 70% of data is used for model training and 30% for testing. Firstly, logistic regression algo is used to build the model and confusion matrix is used to compute different parameters. Then random forest and decision tree classifier is used to build model. Accuracy is calculated from all three models created from discussed three algorithms. After comparative analysis it is found that Random forest possess the highest accuracy of 97% among the applied three algorithms. However lesser time is taken by logistic regression. The dataset used in this work is big and contains 43400 records. Most of the researchers have used dataset possessing records less than 1000. Proposed work does not only build the models using different algorithms but also perform comparative analysis of used algorithms.

6 Conclusion

Healthcare data is growing in diverse and from unreliable data sources from time to time at alarming rate. Heart disease and stroke are world's top two diseases from which humans die. So, it is necessary to build a system which will do earlier detection of these disease. Machine learning with Big Data processing engine spark can handle huge amounts of data and apply machine learning to the same. The proposed work applies distributed machine learning to big dataset using apache spark, it is found that random forest possesses the highest accuracy of 97 percent. The dataset used is imbalanced resulting in obtaining high accuracy.

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